

AN OVERVIEW ON ALKALINE TREATMENTS FOR MODIFICATION OF AGRO-WASTE AND ITS APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture is back bone of Indian economy with year -round crop cultivation and generates large amount of agro-waste. Utilization of agricultural waste is considered to be the important step in environmental protection, energy structure and agricultural development. Recycling of agro waste into value added products is an effective alternative of managing wastes. Agricultural waste are lignocellulosic materials and requires some pretreatments for their modification and conversion into value added products. Alkali pretreatment is found to be most efficient treatments in comparison with other pretreatments and modification methods. Alkali pretreatment leads to alter surface morphology of lignocellulosic agro waste. Most of the lignin content from fibrous agro waste is removed during the treatment. Separated lignin can be recycled and further used for bioethanol generation. The fibrous material derived from agro waste undergo enormous change after alkali treatment. It has good mechanical properties; therefore, it can be molded into lightweight bio composites. Alteration in surface properties such as porosity, surface area and functional groups after treatment brings about material to be a good adsorbent for verities of dyes and heavy metals from waste water. Alkaline pretreatment opens a new era for development of sustainable recycling of fibrous agricultural waste into value added products

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION

The agricultural industry plays a vital role in world economy. The growing food demand has led to tremendous increase in food production. India is second largest economy based on agriculture and agro- products and Maharashtra is third biggest state in which nearly two-third land is acquired for gross crop area. The major crops of Maharashtra are banana, followed by sugarcane, rice, maize, sorghum, pulses, wheat and soybean. Approximately, 230.40 lakh hectares land of the total area in Maharashtra is under cultivation producing approximately 109.58 million tons of agro waste per year. Agricultural operations in Maharashtra provide huge quantity of lignocellulosic material in the form of agricultural waste (1). It comprises crop residue and process residue. Crop residue are field rest, remaining after harvesting such as stalk, stems, leaves, seed stover. The process residues are left after crop is processed into usable resource. Sugarcane bagasse, husks of cereals is some examples of process residue. Both the crop residue and process residue are derived from wheat, rice, sorghum, maize, banana, cotton, soybean, groundnut, oil seeds and sugarcane (2). Residues derived from wheat, maize, sorghum and pulses are commonly used as cattle feed. Study shows that 19.648% of total agro waste generated is used as cattle feed, 19.99% waste is burnt, 4.085% of the crop residues are used for composting while remaining is wasted (3). However, sugarcane biomass, cotton and soybean stalk are not fed to animals due to high lignin and crystalline cellulose content. These wastes are burnt in the field by farmers, though burning of the agro waste is not an ecofriendly method of waste management.

Indian Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE) report indicates that, average 500 million ton (Mt) of agro waste is generated per year and out of this, 140 Mt is burnt each year in India. Considerable portion of agro waste is burnt in India in comparison with other Asian countries and it cause excessive particulate matter emission and air pollution. Disposal of waste has become a complex problem and hence national agencies are continuously developing policies and finding possible options to manage these wastes. It probably includes their conversion to reusable sources.

Use of three R strategies, based on the type of waste and characteristics has been suggested by research scholars and adopted for clean environment(4). However, some pretreatments are required to recycle the waste into value added products which are broadly categorized into physical, chemical, thermochemical and biochemical process (5). The detail classification of pretreatments is described in figure2 (6, 7, 8).

MODIFICATION OF AGRO WASTE

Mechanical processes like crushing, hammering, cutting etc. split ligno cellulosic material into fine particles. It leads to decrease in particle size of material and increase specific surface area. These processes also reduce degree of polymerization and helps for reduction in cellulose crystallinity. The effect of different radiations on agro waste was examined by various research scholars. Studies show that, gamma radiation degrades cellulose into oligosaccharides by breaking the bonds of molecular chains of cellulose and links between hemicellulose and lignin. Ultra sound waves are low energy radiations which enhance efficiency of chemical treatments used for extraction of hemicellulose and lignin, assisting delignification and increase in porosity of material. Research scholar has also focused on the effect of micro wave radiations on lignocellulosic material. It was observed that micro wave radiations cause localized heating producing disruption of lignocellulosic material while microwave- alkali pretreatment has considerable effect on lignin removal. In high temperature pyrolysis process material is heated rapidly and the process results into cellulose decomposition. Physicochemical pretreatments are combination of heat treatment- generally hydrothermal heating along with chemical reagents and mechanical forces. It has fewer negative impacts on environment as less hazardous chemicals and mild reaction conditions are required to bring about the process.

Figure1

Each pretreatment has its advantages as well as disadvantages and the products obtained after pretreatments are highly specific. Basic pretreatments given to lignocellulosic material and products derived after treatments are encapsulated in figure 2.

Many chemical treatments were suggested by research scholars for modification of lignocellulosic material, but alkali treatment is economical, efficient and highly preferred chemical treatment in comparison with other chemical modification methods. Alkali treatment on lignocellulosic material results in swelling which leads to increase in internal surface area, decrease in degree of polymerization and crystallinity (9, 10). The major reaction during alkaline pretreatment leads to dissociation of lignin along with hemicellulose and results in de-esterification of intermolecular ester bonds. Following reaction indicates hydrolysis of ester groups present in lignocellulosic material into carboxylate ion and alcohol in presence of alkali (11).

These carboxylate ions may further provide adsorption sites and improve adsorption capacity of lignocellulosic material after alkali treatment. Effect of alkaline reagents at specific reaction conditions on lignocellulosic material is summarized in table 1 (12, 13, 14).

Table 1 :Alkaline pretreatment reagents and their conditions and effects

Reagent	Reaction conditions				Major chemical changes occurred
	Concentration of reagent	Temperature and pressure	Time	Solid loading	
Sodium hydroxide	0.5 to 10%	60 to 180 ⁰ C	5 to 60 min.	10 to 30%	50% hemicellulose dissolution and 60 to 80% delignification
Sodium carbonate	1 to 30%	60 to 180 ⁰ C	5 to 60 min.	10 to 30%	20 to 40% hemicellulose dissolution and 40 to 60% delignification
Ammonia	5 to 30% ammonium hydroxide	30 to 210 ⁰ C and high pressure	3 to 60 min.	10 to 50%	10 to 50% hemicellulose dissolution and 0 to 80% delignification profound swelling, lignin removal or modification
	10 to 50% gaseous ammonium	25 to 80 ⁰ C	72 hours	50 %	
	Liquid anhydrous ammonia	70 to 90 ⁰ C and 15 to 20 atm pressure	5 minutes	60 to 90%	No hemicellulose dissolution and no lignin removal.
Calcium hydroxide	0.05 to 0.15%	25 to 130 ⁰ C	1 hour to 8 week	5 to 20%	20 to 40% hemicellulose dissolution 60 to 80% delignification.

ROLE OF ALKALI TREATED LIGNOCELLULOSIC MATERIAL IN ETHANOL PRODUCTION

High pressure treatments with sodium hydroxide have considerable effect on the lignocellulosic fraction of fibrous sugarcane waste. The treatment leads to change in the microstructure and crystallinity of material. Due to such modifications, lignocellulosic materials could be used to get fermentable sugars for production of food additives and alcohol (15). Studies show that among all chemical treatments, ammonia treatment significantly remove lignin and large number of phenolic compounds. It results in enhancement of saccharification of agro waste (16). Dewaxing and alkaline pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass showed changes in the plant compositions. A higher yield of sugars and ethanol was observed in dewaxed and alkaline pretreated samples (17). Pretreatment of rice straw with sodium carbonate enhanced the saccharification of rice straw. The analysis clearly confirmed the modification in the structure and chemical composition of rice straw after alkaline pretreatment. Sodium carbonate pretreated rice straw exhibited high enzymatic saccharification therefore, proved an ideal pretreatment process for the production of bioethanol (18).

ROLE OF ALKALI TREATED LIGNOCELLULOSIC MATERIAL IN DESIGNING ADSORBENT

Adsorption is simple economic method for removing organic and inorganic matters from waste water particularly dyes and heavy metals. It has high treatment efficiency and adsorbents can be

regenerated for multiple reuses. Adsorption process is highly selective. Therefore, many attempts have been made by researchers to prepare cellulosic adsorbents by modification of cellulosic material most of the dyes present in wastewater are either positively charged or negatively charged and adsorption occurs due electrostatic forces, van der Waals forces and hydrogen bonding between adsorbent and pollutant molecule (19). Alkaline treatment is found effective for designing low-cost adsorbent. Treatment of lignocellulosic material with Sodium hydroxide not only ruptures the covalent bonding between lignocellulosic material and depolymerize lignin but also hydrolyze hemicellulose. Such structural change enhances the adsorption capacity of material. Sodium hydroxide treatment makes the cellulose material free from fats and waxes and it helps to reveal chemically reactive functional groups like -OH (20). Studies has been reported that alkali treated agro wastes are proven to be efficient adsorbents for dyes like Basic blue, Congo Red, methylene blue and some azo dyes. Along with the dyes heavy metals ions such as Pb^{+2} Cd^{+2} and Zn^{+2} are also removed from waste water by alkali modified lignocellulosic material.(21, 7, 15, 22, 23, 24).

ROLE OF ALKALI TREATED LIGNOCELLULOSIC MATERIAL IN FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

The use of natural fibre reinforced polymer composites has been increased as these are environment friendly composites with good mechanical properties and less dense. Virgin fibres absorb moisture, hence cannot bind properly with resins or binders (25, 10). Alkali treatment changes surface morphology of fibres. It leads to fibrillation of fibre bundles into smaller fibre (26, 27). Alkali based chemical treatments enhance tensile strength of natural fibres. Scouring and bleaching treatments improves fineness of fibre and dark colour due to lignin removal (25). These treatments are also carried in presence of alkali. Functional groups modified after treatment can bind with reagents used for binding the fibres in polymer matrix. Alkali treatment not only decrease the moisture absorption but also improve the interface bonding between reinforcement and matrix (28). The variation in mechanical properties of natural fibre reinforced composites derived from Abaca fibre, bagasse, banana fibre, bamboo fibre due to alkali treatment has been reported by several research scholars. Such composite has wide range of applications in building various components including aircraft interiors, wing boxes, and cabin interior panels (29).

CONCLUSIONS

Agricultural wastes are lignocellulosic materials. It can be converted into value added products by pretreatments and modifications. Alkali treatment is an effective, economical as well as sustainable treatment that brings about surface modification, increase in porosity and surface area. Such changes lead to use the agro waste for ethanol generation as the reaction sites are opened for further modification. It also alters crystallinity, tensile strength and colour of waste lignocellulosic fibres. Substitution of functional groups during the treatment helps to the

adsorption of charged particles like dyes, heavy metals from waste water. Therefore, alkali treated fibrous material would be a green adsorbent that can be recycled into biocomposite. The lignin separated during the treatment can be retained and used for generation of bioethanol. Thus, alkali treatment would be a zero-wastetreatment if it is systematically used for fibre modification.

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